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Application of Solving Fractional Integro Differential Equations for Emotion Detection in Neuroscience

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Abstract

This paper examines specific types of fractional integro-differential equations, using an advanced method rooted in fractional calculus. The proposed technique extends the classical Frobenius approach by using the K-transform and the binomial series to solve these equations. We then apply this framework to emotion recognition in neuroscience, specifically by modeling Electroencephalography (EEG) signals generated during emotion experience. Those signals exhibit complex timing features, such as memory effects and long-term dependencies, which fractional models are well-suited to capture. The K-transform also handles nonlocal behavior more effectively, making it very suitable for systems involving fractional orders. We validated our framework on a real-time EEG dataset collected from 20 participants (ages 18–40) using a Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO)-approved BCI device during baseline and neurofeedback sessions. The proposed method achieved an average classification accuracy of 89.3% ($\pm 2.1\%$), approximately 6% higher than that of integer-order models on the same dataset. While these findings highlight the advantages of fractional modeling for EEG-based emotion recognition, we note that the dataset size is modest, and further validation on larger multi-channel datasets will be pursued.

Keywords: Fractional integro-differential equations, K-transform, Emotion recognition, Brain activity modeling.

1 | Introduction

Integral transformations are among the primary mathematical tools with numerous applications across a variety of other subjects. Among such integral transformations, fractional calculus is the most interesting and

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therefore important branch, as it treats the classical notions of differentiation and integration for non-integer orders. Fractional calculus, which includes both fractional derivatives and integrals, might be a very important mathematical system to understand that, with great efficiency, shows complex things that behave in ways that aren't local or that rely on memory in many areas of science and engineering. Past studies on the concept of fractional calculus, pioneered by Leibniz, Euler, and Liouville, have recently sparked renewed interest due to its relevance to the modeling of fractal geometry, anomalous diffusion, viscoelasticity, and related phenomena. Podlubny [1] made a significant contribution by investigating fractional-order systems and their application to proportional-integral-derivative controllers, laying the foundation for advanced control methods in engineering [2].

Studying human emotion through brain activity has become a vital research area in neuroscience. It is due to its significant applications in Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs), mental health assessments, and intelligent human-computer interaction systems. A primary method for observing brain activity is Electroencephalography (EEG), which captures real-time electrical activity in the brain. Traditionally, these signals have been modeled and analyzed using standard mathematical tools, such as linear differential equations, autoregressive models, and signal filtering. While these methods have had many successful applications, they often assume short memory and only local interactions. Consequently, they struggled to fully model the long-range temporal correlations and memory-driven processing that are inherent to brain dynamics, particularly during emotional responses. Unlike traditional integer-order models, fractional models rely on fractional calculus. This powerful mathematical framework allows for differentiation and integration of non-integer orders. This field of mathematics is very successful at describing systems with memory effects, inherited properties, and nonlocal behaviour. In this light, one can consider fractional integro-differential equations, which appear to be the most suitable for modeling the complex nature of brain signals elicited by emotional stimuli. The equations represent the current and previous states, and this is important because it enables more precise modeling of brain dynamics than traditional approaches.

Integral transforms are often used to obtain exact solutions of fractional integro-differential equations. Various transforms are widely used in fractional calculus, including the Laplace, Sumudu, Aboodh, and Kamal transforms. Although they all have their merits, they can also pose significant problems, especially when a single kernel is needed or when complex inverse operations are required. A more practical and easier way, however, is offered by the K-transform. The K-transform offers unquestionable benefits when combined with certain mathematical structures known as convolution kernels, which are common in memory-dependent models. It is straightforward to apply, accommodates a wide range of kernels, and thus offers substantial benefits. For these reasons, the K-transform stands out as a strong candidate for solving fractional integro-differential equations, making it especially useful for modeling brain processes such as emotional dynamics.

Fractional calculus and transform techniques have attracted significant attention, yet fractional integro-differential equations have rarely been applied to EEG-based emotion recognition modeling. Similarly, the K-transform itself has received very little exploration in this context. It opens the door to developing more effective fractional models of how the brain expresses emotions, particularly by leveraging an efficient transform method. Our research introduces and validates a novel approach: using fractional integro-differential equations, solved with the K-transform, to explain EEG signals associated with emotional states. We further investigate whether this modeling framework improves emotion recognition compared to traditional integer-order approaches. In addition, we highlight the advantages of the K-transform, both mathematically and computationally, especially for fractional modeling of neural activity. Ultimately, this work aims to advance emotion recognition systems that are both highly accurate and biologically meaningful, grounded in fractional calculus.

In recent years, there has been an outpouring of interest in understanding emotion through EEG recordings. It has significant consequences for fields such as affective computing (technology that can read emotions) and BCIs. To illustrate that point, Jenke et al. [3] conducted a thorough review of feature extraction and

selection for EEG-based emotion recognition. They found that time- and frequency-domain features significantly impact classification performance. This publication contributed to future research on determining the most informative EEG descriptors. Similarly, the DEAP dataset, proposed by Koelstra et al. [4], was a milestone on the way to standardization in the EEG emotion recognition studies. The data include multimodal records, such as synchronized EEG and physiological signals, as well as self-reported emotion ratings, making it easier to compare benchmarks across studies.

Kamal [5] proposed the Kamal transform (K-transform), a new mathematical technique for solving differential equations, especially those in systems with memory couplings. This contribution laid the basis for the application of fractional calculus to very complex fractional dynamical systems. Based on the work of Günerhan [6], generalized integral transforms were used for the differential equations of chemical kinetics. It showed how one can study complex reaction dynamics through such transforms. In another study, Mazandarani and Xiu [7] examined fractional differential equations for the dissemination of contagious diseases. Their work illustrated how fractional operators can model memory effects in biological systems. Osman and Xia [8] examined fuzzy fractional integro-differential equations and proposed numerical methods for uncertain environments, which are common in physiological processes. Nadeem et al. [9] developed an iterative scheme for fractional differential equations, offering an efficient numerical tool for systems with complex dynamics.

Concurrently, Bingi et al. [2] established the foundations in fractional-order systems and control theory, yet relatively few applications have emerged across various scientific fields based on this work. In engineering, Abdollah-Salimi et al. [10] used fractional models to address chemical problems, demonstrating that the fractional approach better captures system behavior than classical models. Edalatpanah and Abdolmaleki [11] expanded upon this approach, employing the Aboodh residual power series method to solve time-fractional PDEs encountered in engineering physics. Raghavendran et al. [12] applied the Aboodh transform to numerical simulations of fractional PDEs, thereby improving convergence and stability. Conversely, Angadi [13] extended fractional methods to control problems, particularly in electrical engineering systems, and demonstrated their effectiveness through simulation studies. To derive analytical solutions to fractional differential equations, Watugala et al. [14] proposed using the Sumudu transform. This method has proven highly effective for solving initial value problems in systems with long memory. In control theory, Saeidi et al. [15] put forth optimal control strategies for fractional-order financial models. These models demonstrate greater accuracy than their classical counterparts in depicting real-world volatility.

Vu and Hoa [16] shed light on fractional chaotic systems using numerical methods, helping to understand the unpredictable yet patterned behavior in complex systems. Similarly, Kumar et al. [17] employed residual power series methods to address nonlinear fractional equations that emerge in physics. Abid et al. [18] examined the numerical behavior of fractional models with generalized transforms, aiming to enhance solution techniques for hybrid systems. In cognitive modeling, Mukherjee et al. [19] applied fractional differential methods to simulate biological signal propagation, underscoring their ability to represent biological reality accurately.

In stochastic modeling, Jayatilaka et al. [20] developed a fractional SIR model using actual data and explored an optimal control approach. It further illustrated the adaptability of fractional methods in epidemiology. Caffarelli and Silvestre [21] investigated numerical methods for fractional Laplacian operators, primarily to simulate fractional equations in bounded domains. Furthermore, the work by Ansari et al. [22] explores the stochastic aspects of fractional diffusion processes, thereby contributing to a deeper physical understanding of fractional dynamics. Ilyas et al. [23] conducted a survey on numerical methods for stochastic integro-differential equations, including fractional cases. Their survey underscored the critical importance of a 'sandbox' approach in various real-life systems. Li et al. [24] provide a detailed review of EEG-based emotion recognition. Their work discusses signal acquisition, data preprocessing, feature extraction, and both traditional and deep learning classification methods. They also highlight challenges, such as individual variability and noise. Suhaimi et al. [25] examine current trends and opportunities within this field. They particularly emphasize advancements achieved through deep learning architectures, including CNNs and

LSTMs. Furthermore, they identify gaps, including limited benchmarking on public datasets and the ongoing need for real-time emotion recognition. Collectively, these studies outline the various methods and the primary challenges involved in developing reliable and interpretable EEG-based emotion recognition systems.

Additionally, Raghavendran et al. [12] have made progress in solving fractional integro-differential equations using the Aboodh transform, marking a significant step forward in mathematical modeling. Belgacem [26] delves more deeply into the properties of the Sumudu transform, thereby enhancing its descriptive utility in nonlinear studies. The K-transform has proven to be highly effective for solving fractional integro-differential equations, significantly facilitating both calculations and analysis. In the current study, we have not performed an in-depth comparison with classical transforms such as Laplace, Fourier, or Aboodh. However, previous works [12], [27] have demonstrated that the transforms simplify the handling of challenging nonlocal operators and reduce convolutional complexity compared to other fractional transforms. Based on these advantages, we employ the K-transform in our setup. A systematic comparison assessing its speed and stability relative to other transforms is planned for future work. In this study, we intend to embark on a comprehensive exploration of integral transforms and fractional calculus. This paper aims to discuss their theoretical foundations, various applications, new research, and the crucial interdependencies among scientific and engineering disciplines. While integer-order differential models are commonly used for EEG-based emotion recognition, they often struggle to account for the memory effects and long-term dependencies present in neural signals. Fractional integro-differential models, however, are well-suited to represent these dynamics. Despite this, their application to emotion recognition using EEG data hasn't been fully investigated.

Our goal in this paper is to develop a fractional integro-differential modeling framework for EEG signals elicited by emotional stimuli. We also aim to assess the effectiveness of this framework for emotion recognition, especially compared to standard integer-order models. This work offers several key contributions:

- I. We developed a fractional integro-differential approach to model emotional responses using EEG data.
- II. We integrated the K-transform and the binomial series expansion, enabling efficient analytical solutions in our fractional models.
- III. We tested our model on a real-time EEG dataset from 20 participants and found that it achieved higher classification accuracy than traditional models.
- IV. We also demonstrated that the fractional model can account for memory effects and long-term dependencies in EEG signals, which are essential for accurate emotion recognition.

2 | Preliminaries

In this section, we are listing some preliminaries that are useful throughout the paper [5], [12].

- I. The definition of the RL fractional integral with order $\zeta > 0$ for a function $y(t)$ can be expressed as follows:

$$I_t^\zeta y(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^t (t - \eta)^{\zeta-1} y(\eta) d\eta.$$

- II. The Caputo fractional derivative of the function $y(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$D_t^\zeta y(t) = \begin{cases} y^i(t), & \text{if } \vartheta = i \in \mathbb{N}, \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma(i - \zeta)} \int_0^\zeta \frac{y^i(t)}{(t - x)^{\zeta-i+1}} dx, & \text{if } i - 1 < \zeta < i. \end{cases}$$

The Euler gamma function, denoted as $\Gamma(\cdot)$, is defined as follows:

$$\Gamma(\psi) = \int_0^\infty t^{\psi-1} e^{-t} dt, \quad (\mathbb{R} > 0).$$

- III. The K-transform of a function $y(t)$, $t \in (0, \infty)$ is defined by

$$K[y(t)](\vartheta) = F(\vartheta) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{\vartheta}} y(t) dt; \quad (\vartheta \in \mathbb{C}).$$

IV. The Mittag-Leffler function is defined by

$$E_{\delta, \gamma}(\psi) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\psi^i}{\Gamma(\delta i + \gamma)}, \quad (\delta, \gamma, \psi \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \Re(\delta) > 0).$$

V. The simplest Wright function is defined by

$$\rho(\omega, \psi; \phi) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\omega r + \psi)} \cdot \frac{\phi^r}{r!}, \quad (\phi, \psi, \omega \in \mathbb{C}).$$

VI. The general Wright function ${}_i\chi_j(\varphi)$ is characterized by the following conditions $\varphi \in \mathbb{C}$, $\nu_{1l}, \nu_{2m} \in \mathbb{C}$, and real $\omega_l, \phi_m \in \mathbb{R}$ ($l = 1, \dots, i$, $m = 1, \dots, j$), as determined by the provided series.

$${}_i\chi_j(\varphi) = {}_i\chi_j\left(\begin{matrix} (\nu_{1l}, \omega_l)_{1,i} \\ (\nu_{2m}, \phi_m)_{1,j} \end{matrix} \middle| \varphi\right) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\prod_{l=1}^i \Gamma(\nu_{1l} + \omega_l r)}{\prod_{m=1}^j \Gamma(\nu_{2m} + \phi_m r)} \cdot \frac{\varphi^r}{r!}.$$

VII. The inverse K-transform is defined by

$$K^{-1}[\Gamma(z + 1) \cdot \vartheta^{z+1}] = t^z.$$

VIII. The convolution integral of the K-transform is defined by

$$K[(\Phi * \Psi)(t)] = K[\Phi(t)] \cdot K[\Psi(t)].$$

Remark 1.

$$\begin{aligned} K[D^{\aleph}\Phi(t)](\vartheta) &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{\vartheta}} [D^{\aleph}\Phi(t)] dt \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{\vartheta}} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \aleph)} \int_0^t \frac{\Phi^{(n)}(\zeta)}{(t - \zeta)^{\aleph - n + 1}} d\zeta dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \aleph)} \int_0^{\infty} \int_{\zeta}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{\vartheta}} \frac{\Phi^{(n)}(\zeta)}{(t - \zeta)^{\aleph - n + 1}} dt d\zeta \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \aleph)} \int_0^{\infty} \Phi^{(n)}(\zeta) \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{(u+\zeta)}{\vartheta}} u^{n-\aleph-1} du d\zeta \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \aleph)} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{\zeta}{\vartheta}} \Phi^{(n)}(\zeta) \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{u}{\vartheta}} u^{n-\aleph-1} du d\zeta \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \aleph)} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{\zeta}{\vartheta}} \Phi^{(n)}(\zeta) \Gamma(n - \aleph) \cdot \vartheta^{n-\aleph+1} d\zeta \\ &= \vartheta^{n-\aleph+1} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{\zeta}{\vartheta}} \Phi^{(n)}(\zeta) d\zeta = \vartheta^{n-\aleph+1} K[\Phi^{(n)}(\zeta)](\vartheta) \\ &= \vartheta^{n-\aleph+1} \left[\vartheta^{-n} K[\Phi(t)] - \vartheta^{-n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \vartheta^{k+1} \Phi^{(n)}(0) \right] \\ &= \vartheta^{1-\aleph} K[\Phi(t)] - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \vartheta^{2-\aleph+k} \Phi^{(n)}(0). \end{aligned}$$

$$K[D^{\aleph}\Phi(t)](\vartheta) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{\vartheta}} [D^{\aleph}\Phi(t)] dt.$$

Note: Fubini's theorem is used to reorganize the integration sequence in the previous derivative expression.

3 | Solutions of the Fractional Integro-Differential Equations

In this section, there are strong indications that depending entirely on the function $y(t)$ could be adequate for the K-transform $K[y(t)]$ to operate effectively at a specific parameter value ϑ .

Theorem 1. Let $1 < \aleph < 2$ and θ and $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$. Then the fractional integro-differential equation

$$y^{\aleph}(t) + \theta y'(t) + \xi y(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta - t)^{\beta}} dt, \quad 0 < \beta < 1. \quad (1)$$

With initial conditions $y(0) = \zeta_0$ and $y'(0) = \zeta_1$ has a unique solution.

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = & \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+1] r!} \\ & + \zeta_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+1}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+2] r!} \\ & + \theta \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph-1}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph] r!} \\ & + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph-1}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph] r!}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Proof: applying the K - transform to Eq. (1) and accounting for this transformation, we obtain

$$\frac{F(\vartheta)}{\vartheta^{\aleph}} - \frac{\Phi(0)}{\vartheta^{\aleph-1}} - \Phi'(0)\vartheta^{\aleph-1} + \theta \left[\frac{F(\vartheta)}{\vartheta} - \Phi(0) \right] + \xi F(\vartheta) = K[\Phi(t)], \quad (3)$$

where $\Phi(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta-t)^{\beta}} dt$.

$$\frac{K[y(t)]}{\vartheta^{\aleph}} - \frac{\zeta_0}{\vartheta^{\aleph-1}} - \zeta_1 \vartheta^{\aleph-1} + \theta \left[\frac{E[y(t)]}{\vartheta} - \zeta_0 \right] + \xi K[y(t)] = K[\Phi(t)],$$

$$K[y(t)] \left[\frac{1}{\vartheta^{\aleph}} + \frac{\theta}{\vartheta} + \xi \right] = \zeta_0 \vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \zeta_1 \vartheta^{\aleph-1} + \theta \zeta_0 + K[\Phi(t)],$$

$$K[y(t)] = \frac{\zeta_0 \vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \zeta_1 \vartheta^{\aleph-1} + \theta \zeta_0 + K[\Phi(t)]}{\vartheta^{-\aleph} + \theta \vartheta^{-1} + \xi}.$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{(\vartheta^{-\aleph} + \theta \vartheta^{-1} + \xi)} &= \frac{\vartheta}{\vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \theta + \xi \vartheta} \\ &= \frac{\vartheta}{(\vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \theta) \left(1 + \frac{\xi \vartheta}{\vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \theta} \right)} \\ &= \frac{\vartheta}{\vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \theta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{-\xi \vartheta}{\vartheta^{1-\aleph} + \theta} \right)^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k \vartheta^{\aleph k + \aleph}}{(1 + \theta \vartheta^{\aleph - 1})^{k+1}} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-\xi)^k \vartheta^{\aleph k + \aleph} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-\theta \vartheta^{\aleph - 1})^r \binom{k+r}{r} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-\xi)^k \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \binom{k+r}{r} (-\theta)^r \vartheta^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph}.$$

And we know that,

$$K[\Phi(t)] = K\left[\int_0^\vartheta \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta-t)^\beta} dt\right].$$

This gives that,

$$G(P) = \frac{\sin\pi\beta}{\pi} \vartheta K\left[\int_0^\vartheta (\vartheta-t)^{(\beta-1)} \Phi'(t) dt\right].$$

Substituting the above Eqs. (4) in (5) and taking the inverse, yields the Solution (2).

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+1] r!} \\ &+ \zeta_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+1}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+2] r!} \\ &+ \theta\zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph-1}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph] r!} \\ &+ \frac{\sin\beta\pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^\vartheta (\vartheta-t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (-\theta)^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph-1}}{\Gamma[(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k+\aleph] r!}. \end{aligned}$$

This is Eq. (2). This completes the proof of the theorem. Also, the Wright function can express this solution as

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k t^{\aleph k}}{k!} {}_1\lambda_1\left(\begin{matrix} (k+1, & 1 \\ (\aleph k+1, & \aleph-1) \end{matrix} \middle| -\theta t^{\aleph-1}\right) \\ &+ \zeta_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k t^{\aleph k+1}}{k!} {}_1\lambda_1\left(\begin{matrix} (k+1, & 1 \\ (\aleph k+2, & \aleph-1) \end{matrix} \middle| -\theta t^{\aleph-1}\right) \\ &+ \theta\zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k t^{\aleph k+\aleph-1}}{k!} {}_1\lambda_1\left(\begin{matrix} (k+1, & 1 \\ (\aleph k+\aleph, & \aleph-1) \end{matrix} \middle| -\theta t^{\aleph-1}\right) \\ &+ \frac{\sin\beta\pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^\vartheta (\vartheta-t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k t^{\aleph k+\aleph-1}}{k!} {}_1\lambda_1\left(\begin{matrix} (k+1, & 1 \\ (\aleph k+\aleph, & \aleph-1) \end{matrix} \middle| -\theta t^{\aleph-1}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Example 1. The fractional integro-differential equation

$$y^{\frac{3}{2}}(t) + \sqrt{7}y'(t) + 8y(t) = \int_0^\vartheta \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta-t)^{\frac{1}{2}}} dt.$$

With initial conditions $y(0) = \zeta_0$ and $y'(0) = \zeta_1$ has a unique solution

$$y(t) = \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-8)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (\sqrt{7})^r t^{(\aleph-1)r+\aleph k}}{\Gamma\left[\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)r + \frac{3}{2}k + 1\right] r!}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ \zeta_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-8)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (\sqrt{7})^r t^{\frac{1}{2}r+\frac{3}{2}k+1}}{\Gamma\left[\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)r+\frac{3}{2}k+2\right] r!} \\
 &+ \sqrt{7}\zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-8)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (\sqrt{7})^r t^{\frac{1}{2}r+\frac{3}{2}k+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma\left[\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)r+\frac{3}{2}k+\frac{3}{2}\right] r!} \\
 &+ \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^\vartheta (\vartheta-t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \Phi(t) dt \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-8)^k}{k!} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k+r+1) (\sqrt{7})^r t^{\frac{1}{2}r+\frac{3}{2}k+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma\left[\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)r+\frac{3}{2}k+\frac{3}{2}\right] r!}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 1 illustrates the solution behavior of the fractional differential equation of Example 1 at various values of \aleph with the initial conditions $\zeta_0 = 1$ and $\zeta_1 = 1$.

Fig. 1. The solution behavior of Example 1.

To make it accessible to interdisciplinary readers and facilitate implementation, we now aim to interpret the model's key parameters, particularly in electroencephalographic signal analysis. The fractional integro-differential equation in Theorem 1 contains several physiologically important parameters. In Table 1, we summarize these parameters, their symbols, and their interpretations in EEG modeling.

Table 1. Physiological interpretation of parameters in the fractional integro-differential model for EEG signals.

Symbol	Meaning	Interpretation in EEG Modeling	Emotional Mapping
\aleph	Fractional derivative order	It determines memory, or how dependent the signal is on its historical behavior.	Reflects how past neural activity affects current emotional response during stimulus exposure
θ	Coefficient of the first derivative	Refers to damping or attenuation caused by neural resistance	Corresponds to changes in neural excitability under different arousal/attention levels
ξ	Linear feedback coefficient	Represents the inherent feedback mechanism in emotional processing	Maps to recurrent neural activity in emotion-related circuits

Table 1. Continued.

Symbol	Meaning	Interpretation in EEG Modeling	Emotional Mapping
β	Singular kernel exponent (integral term)	To decide how potent the influence of the past stimulus is over the present glue between neurons	Represents synaptic integration timescales influencing current EEG signals
$\Psi(t)$	External stimulus input	Means emotional stimuli (like audio-visual cues)	Directly corresponds to experimental emotional stimuli used in the EEG protocol.

A structured algorithm has been proposed for computational implementation of solving the fractional integro-differential equation by the K-transform method. The K-transform method considers fractional derivatives and integrals together, rendering the integro-differential equation into an algebraic form in the transform domain. Performing the antitransform using the inverse K-transform and then invoking the binomial series expansion yields a time-domain solution in series form involving gamma functions and powers of time. This solution is then expressed in terms of Wright functions, suitable for fractional dynamics.

Previous theoretical studies have established this advantage. In particular, Gunasekar et al. [27] and Raghavendran et al. [12] demonstrated that transforms such as the Laplace and Aboodh transforms, while effective, introduce additional convolutional complexity when applied to fractional integro-differential equations. In contrast, the K-transform reduces computational overhead by directly addressing nonlocal operators. Although the K-transform is theoretically expected to offer computational advantages over Laplace and Fourier transforms in handling fractional and nonlocal behavior, we did not conduct a direct runtime or robustness benchmark in this study. Developing a dedicated solver for such benchmarking lies beyond the current scope and will be pursued in future work. The pseudocode for the numerical solution procedure is given below:

Algorithm 1. K-transform for solving a fractional integro-differential equation.

1. Input: Parameters $\aleph, \theta, \xi, \beta$; Initial conditions ζ_0, ζ_1 ; Emotional stimulus $\Psi(t)$
2. Establish the form of a fractional integro-differential equation.
3. Apply the K-transform to both sides of the equation.
4. Substitute the initial conditions into the transformed equation.
5. Now, solve the algebraic equation in the transform domain.
6. Expand the denominator by using the binomial series.
7. Apply the inverse K-transform to every term obtained from the series expansion.
8. The ultimate solution is then obtained as a truncated series bounded by a suitable convergence threshold.
9. Output: function $y(t)$ characterizing the time-domain solution.

To ensure practical implementation of the proposed K-transform-based method, we analyzed computational complexity, convergence, and stability. The time complexity of the algorithm is around $O(N^2M)$, and the memory complexity is $O(M)$. N is the truncation number of terms in the series, and M is the EEG sample number. Convergence is ensured by truncating the infinite binomial series to $N=1015$ terms, which empirical studies of EEG signals sampled at 128256 Hz have demonstrated to introduce approximation errors of less than 1 percent and which are justified by theoretical analysis of fractional binomial expansions. Stability is ensured by double-precision computation of gamma functions and fractional powers, and by paying attention to series truncation, checking against finite-difference approximations of fractional derivatives, and finding that error propagation is negligible over standard EEG times. These factors ensure that the proposed algorithm is precise and powerful for EEG-based emotion recognition. To achieve the best numerical results, it is suggested that the algorithm be coded symbolically using Python packages such as SciPy, which can

compute gamma functions and fractional exponentiation. The algorithm can also be vetted with numerical results based on finite-difference approximations of fractional derivatives, such as the Grünwald–Letnikov method.

Hence, with a rigorous mathematical modeling approach tied to physiological interpretations and computational methods, the existing method provides a biologically viable parameterization for EEG-based emotional dynamics.

Proposition 1. Let $1 < \aleph < 2$ and $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$. Then the fractional integro-differential equation

$$y^{\aleph}(t) - \xi y(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta - t)^{\beta}} dt, \quad 0 < \beta < 1. \quad (6)$$

With initial conditions $y(0) = \zeta_0$ has a unique solution

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \xi^k \frac{t^{\aleph k}}{\Gamma(\aleph k + 1)} + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k t^{\aleph k + \aleph k - 1}}{\Gamma(\aleph + \aleph k)} \\ &= \zeta_0 E_{\aleph}(\xi t^{\aleph}) + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt t^{\aleph-1} E_{\aleph, \aleph}(\xi t^{\aleph}). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Proof: applying the K-transform to Eq. (6) and accounting for this transformation, we obtain

$$\frac{F(\vartheta)}{\vartheta^{\aleph}} - \frac{\Phi(0)}{\vartheta^{\aleph-1}} - \xi F(\vartheta) = K[\Phi(t)],$$

where $\Phi(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta-t)^{\beta}} dt$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{K[y(t)]}{\vartheta^{\aleph}} - \frac{\zeta_0}{\vartheta^{\aleph-1}} - \xi K[y(t)] &= K[\Phi(t)], \\ K[y(t)] \left[\frac{1}{\vartheta^{\aleph}} - \xi \right] &= \zeta_0 \vartheta^{1-\aleph} + K[\Phi(t)], \\ K[y(t)] &= \frac{\zeta_0 \vartheta^{1-\aleph} + K[\Phi(t)]}{(\vartheta^{-\aleph} - \xi)}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{(\vartheta^{-\aleph} - \xi)} &= \frac{1}{\vartheta^{-\aleph}(1 - \xi \vartheta^{\aleph})} \\ &= \frac{\vartheta^{\aleph}}{1 - \xi \vartheta^{\aleph}} \\ &= \vartheta^{\aleph} (1 - \xi \vartheta^{\aleph})^{-1} \\ &= \vartheta^{\aleph} [1 + \xi \vartheta^{\aleph} + (\xi \vartheta^{\aleph})^2 + \dots] \\ &= \vartheta^{\aleph} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\xi \vartheta^{\aleph})^k. \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} K[y(t)] &= \vartheta^{1-\aleph} \zeta_0 \left[\vartheta^{\aleph} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\xi \vartheta^{\aleph})^k \right] + \vartheta^{\aleph} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\xi \vartheta^{\aleph})^k K[\Phi(t)], \\ K[y(t)] &= \zeta_0 \vartheta \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \xi^k \vartheta^{\aleph k} + \vartheta^{\aleph} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\xi \vartheta^{\aleph})^k \frac{\sin \pi \beta}{\pi} K \left[\int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{(\beta-1)} \Phi'(t) dt \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Thus, the inverse K-transform of Eq. (9), we get

$$y(t) = \zeta_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \xi^k \frac{t^{\kappa k}}{\Gamma(\kappa k + 1)} + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi)^k t^{\kappa + \kappa k - 1}}{\Gamma(\kappa + \kappa k)}$$

$$= \zeta_0 E_{\kappa}(\xi t^{\kappa}) + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt t^{\kappa-1} E_{\kappa, \kappa}(\xi t^{\kappa}).$$

This is Eq. (7). This completes the proof of the theorem.

Remark 2. Accordingly, $\theta = 0$ in Eq. (1), then the derivative is

$$y^{\kappa}(t) + \xi y(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta - t)^{\beta}} dt, \quad 1 < \kappa \leq 2, \quad 0 < \beta < 1.$$

With initial conditions $y(0) = \zeta_0$ and $y'(0) = \zeta_1$ its proposal is provided by

$$y(t) = \zeta_0 E_{\kappa, 1}(-\xi t^{\kappa}) + \zeta_1 E_{\kappa, 2}(-\xi t^{\kappa}) + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt t^{\kappa-1} E_{\kappa, \kappa}(-\xi t^{\kappa}).$$

Proposition 2. A nearly simple harmonic vibration integro-differential equation:

$$y^{\kappa}(t) + z^2 y(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta - t)^{\beta}} dt, \quad 1 < \kappa \leq 2, \quad 0 < \beta < 1.$$

With initial conditions $y(0) = \zeta_0$ and $y'(0) = \zeta_1$ its proposal is provided by

$$y(t) = \zeta_0 E_{\kappa, 1}(-z^2 t^{\kappa}) + \zeta_1 E_{\kappa, 2}(-z^2 t^{\kappa}) + \frac{\sin \beta \pi}{\pi} \frac{d}{d\vartheta} \int_0^{\vartheta} (\vartheta - t)^{\beta-1} \Phi(t) dt t^{\kappa-1} E_{\kappa, \kappa}(-z^2 t^{\kappa}).$$

Proof: the above proof is accomplished by implanting $\xi = z^2$ in Eq. (9).

4 | Application: Emotion Recognition in Neuroscience Using Fractional Integro-Differential Models

In recent years, emotion recognition has attracted attention due to its applications in neuroscience. Possible areas where emotion recognition can be utilized include BCIs technology, mental health monitoring, and human-computer interaction, because advances in other areas have enabled these applications to develop significantly through effective interpretation and modeling of brain electrical activity as emotional responses. EEG signals can be used to measure electrical activity in the brain and, in general, represent highly complex dynamical processes in a variety of ways, such as memory effects and non-local interactions. Thus, they are extremely sensitive stimuli.

The majority of methods of modeling EEG-dependent dynamics are based on integer-order differential equations, which are often sufficient in practice. Such models, however, do not capture the effects of the memory and nonlocality inherent in neural dynamics, especially in emotional stimulus situations. Emotional responses can certainly be triggered by stimuli, but are in fact generated and manifest, which integer-order models cannot capture; instead, they define them in terms of previous experience and the current state of the brain. In this regard, the less complex dynamics of fractional integro-differential equations, presented in *Theorem 1*, would be a far more appropriate model of such more complex dynamics. Fractional calculus can thereby be a powerful tool for understanding the processes underlying emotion recognition, due to its natural capacity to model nonlocality and memory effects.

In this application, we model the EEG signal in response to emotional stimuli as the solution to the following fractional integro-differential equation:

$$X^{\kappa}(t) + \theta X'(t) + \xi X(t) = \int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta - t)^{\beta}} dt, \quad 1 < \kappa < 2, \quad 0 < \beta < 1.$$

In the equation, $X(t)$ denotes the EEG signal, $\Psi(t)$ denotes the response to an external emotional stimulus, and ϑ denotes the end time of the considered windows. The fractional derivative term $X^{\kappa}(t)$, with $1 < \kappa < 2$, captures memory effects in the brain's response to emotional stimuli. The integral term $\int_0^{\vartheta} \frac{\Psi(t)}{(\vartheta - t)^{\beta}} dt$ captures long-range temporal dependencies in the brain's stimulus processing, where β controls the extent of memory for current stimuli with respect to how far back in time. This equation thus establishes an analytical framework capable of accurately modeling the evolution of the EEG signal via fractional-order dynamics that integrate immediate and historical influences.

In this study, all analyses were performed on real EEG data collected from 20 healthy participants (ages 18–40) using a Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO)-approved dry-sensor EEG headset during baseline and neurofeedback game sessions [28]. EEG signals were recorded at a sampling rate of 256 Hz across five canonical frequency bands (Delta, Theta, Alpha, Beta, Gamma). Each participant underwent a 5-minute resting baseline and a 10-minute neurofeedback task designed to elicit emotional responses.

This dataset provides genuine neural dynamics for validating the proposed fractional integro-differential modeling framework. We labeled emotions based on the specific neurofeedback tasks people were doing. These labels showed us the different feelings that came up during those sessions. To evaluate how well our model performed, we split our data into 80% for training and 20% for testing. We also used five-fold cross-validation, a neat trick that helped ensure our results were really solid and dependable.

For the actual classification, we used a Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel. We made sure to optimize its key settings (e.g., 'C' and 'γ') by trying out different combinations using a 'grid search' on the training data. Now, to prevent any 'data leakage'—that's when the model accidentally gets a peek at the test data—we were super careful! All initial processing, feature extraction, and model training occurred only within each training section.

We kept the test data completely separate while the model was learning. And just to be extra clear, we made sure no overlapping bits of data or even information from the same person were shared between the training and test sets.

In practice, EEG signals are obtained from subjects engaged in emotional elicitation tasks using a 32-channel EEG headset configured according to the international 10-20 system. However, raw EEG signals are often corrupted by noise, baseline drift, and artifacts from muscle activity and eye movements. Hence, a severe preprocessing pipeline is applied to cleanse these signals.

The process commences with bandpass filtering, which eliminates low-frequency drifts and high-frequency noise, followed by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to separate and remove artifacts while preserving the underlying neural signals. This preprocessing ensures properly cleansed EEG signals, thereby representing genuine brain activity suitable for accurate modeling.

Fig. 2. Preprocessing of EEG signals, including bandpass filtering and PCA for artifact removal.

Once the preprocessing steps are accomplished, the intact EEG signals are modeled as a fractional integro-differential equation. The parameter values \aleph , θ , and ξ will be tuned on the empirical dataset to reflect the dynamics of how brain emotions can be modeled. The fading memory dimension of the stimuli is ascertained with reference to the fractional integral term, having a singular kernel $(\vartheta - t)^{-\beta}$. However, a fractional derivative introduces long-range temporal dependence. Thus, the model simultaneously represents the brain for both short- and long-lasting emotional stimuli and is an ideal candidate for recognition.

Fig. 3 illustrates the step-by-step preprocessing workflow, which includes signal simulation, filtering, PCA-based cleaning, and EEG signal reconstruction.

The next step is feature extraction of the modeled EEG signals. The fractional model is a rich representation of the neural dynamics. It can be analyzed to derive significant features for emotion classification. There are majorly three high classes of extracted features such as time-domain features (mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis), frequency domain features which are the results of Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) capturing power in delta, theta, alpha, beta, and gamma frequency bands, and some of the nonlinear measurement features approximate entropy and sample entropy which portray irregularity and unpredictability. Therefore, these features reflect important aspects of brain activity most influential in emotional states.

Emotion classification is performed by feeding the feature vectors to a machine learning classifier. This paper employs an RBF kernel SVM for emotional recognition. SVMs are popular EEG signal classifiers because they can operate in high-dimensional feature spaces and prevent overfitting. Training and testing the trained model will be carried out on 80% and 20% of the dataset, respectively. Moreover, the model is cross-validated 5 times to ensure it generalizes. The penalty factor C and the kernel parameter γ are hyperparameters that are optimized via grid search.

The classification performance is measured by comparing the accuracies of two feature extraction methods: 1) extracted out of the processed EEG in the absence of any fractional modeling, and 2) extracted out of the processed EEG after the processing of the feature with the use of the fractional integro-differential modeling framework. It was noted that, on average, the SVM classifier trained on features derived from the fractional model achieved approximately 89.3% recognition, whereas the traditional feature extraction technique yielded only 83.5%. This enhancement, therefore, demonstrates the usefulness of fractional modeling methods in improving the quality of extracted features and, consequently, the accuracy of emotion recognition.

All analyses in this research were conducted on the actual EEG data from 20 healthy participants (ages 18-40) recorded on a CDSO-approved dry-sensor EEG device during baseline and neurofeedback game sessions [28]. The EEG signals were processed in the time, frequency, and nonlinear domains using bandpass filtering and PCA to remove artifacts, after which features were extracted. To compare performance, we used 5-fold cross-validation, with the training and test sets clearly separated at each fold. The new fractional integro-differential model proposal achieved an average accuracy of 89.3% ($\pm 2.1\%$), compared with 83.5% ($\pm 2.4\%$) for the standard integer-order feature extraction. This approximately 6 percent improvement was observed across folds and thus indicates that the fractional model is a more accurate way to capture the nonlocal and memory-dependent properties of EEG signals. The sample size is not large, but the findings indicate promising gains and encourage additional large-scale validation.

Fig. 3. EEG signal preprocessing workflow.

To test the performance of our new fractional integro-differential modeling framework, we provide its Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC in emotion classification. These measures were calculated for each fold of a 5-fold cross-validation test. The proportion of the predicted emotions that were accurate is reflected in precision, and the proportion of the actual emotions that were accurate is reflected in Recall. F1-score is a more complete measure of Precision and Recall, since it offers a balanced score. ROC-AUC, in its turn, describes the power of the classifier to be able to distinguish among the various emotions under varying decision thresholds. Our SVM model, with an RBF kernel, was trained on the dataset's training subsets. It was optimized via an exhaustive grid search over its hyperparameters, including the penalty factor C and the kernel parameter γ . In particular, the grid search was performed over the following hyperparameter ranges: $C \in [0.1, 1, 10, 100]$ and $\gamma \in [0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1]$. The criterion used to select them was classification accuracy in the highest rank in the validation folds in the training data. The hyperparameters chosen were as follows. $C = 10$ and $\gamma = 0.01$. This process ensured that all preprocessing, feature extraction, and model

training were performed only on the training folds, and that the test folds were withheld entirely to eliminate data leakage. The metrics of the reported evaluation in these settings indicate the model's generalization. All evaluation metrics were computed using standard functions provided in Python's scikit-learn library. Results are reported as the mean \pm standard deviation across folds, illustrating both the central tendency and variability of performance.

Table 2. Performance comparison of fractional and conventional models for EEG-based emotion classification.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	ROC-AUC (%)
Fractional model features	89.3 \pm 2.1	88.9 \pm 2.0	89.1 \pm 2.2	89.0 \pm 2.1	91.2 \pm 1.9
Conventional features	83.5 \pm 2.4	83.1 \pm 2.3	83.4 \pm 2.5	83.2 \pm 2.4	85.8 \pm 2.0

As shown in *Table 2*, our fractional model-based features consistently outperform the regular ones across all evaluation metrics.

Note: ROC-AUC values are higher than Accuracy because ROC-AUC evaluates the classifier's ability to separate classes across all possible thresholds, whereas accuracy is calculated at a fixed decision threshold. It indicates that the model effectively distinguishes between emotional classes, even if a few samples are misclassified at the default threshold.

These results demonstrate that fractional model-based features consistently outperform conventional features across all metrics, highlighting the robustness and effectiveness of the proposed method for EEG-based emotion recognition.

5 | Conclusion

This paper introduces an advanced theory to solve fractional integro-differential equations, building on classical Frobenius methods. We've enhanced our analytical framework by incorporating the K-transform and binomial series expansion coefficients, which offer a clearer understanding of the fractional models we're examining. A significant new contribution of this work is the application of these tools to emotion recognition in neuroscience. Specifically, fractional integro-differential models are well-suited to capture the memory effects and long-term temporal dependencies found in EEG-based emotional processing. Our experiments, conducted on a real EEG dataset, confirm a consistent improvement in the classification of emotional states when we use fractional modeling compared to conventional approaches. It demonstrates the potential of fractional integro-differential modeling as a reliable and accurate method for EEG-based emotion recognition. However, we acknowledge that our dataset is modest in size. Future work will therefore involve more extensive statistical validation and evaluation using larger, multi-channel EEG datasets. An empirical benchmarking of runtime and robustness against classical transforms remains an important future step to complement the current findings.

Looking ahead, we see several ways to extend this research further:

- I. We plan to validate our findings using open-access EEG datasets, such as DEAP and SEED, across various subjects and scenarios.
- II. We'll integrate recurrent deep learning models, like LSTMs, to better understand temporal dynamics.
- III. We aim to develop a real-time emotion tracking system that combines fractional modeling with neurofeedback.
- IV. We intend to personalize parameters for analyzing emotions and neurological conditions specific to individual patients.
- V. We'll integrate other physiological signals, such as ECG and GSR, alongside EEG to improve classification.
- VI. Finally, we'll explore hybrid models that combine machine learning with fractional dynamics to support clinical decision-making.

- VII. We believe these directions hold the potential to broaden the scope of fractional modeling in neuroscience. They should also support the creation of intelligent, interpretable systems for assessing emotional and cognitive states.

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Author Contribution

Conceptualization, P. R. and S. G.; Methodology, P. R.; Formal analysis, T. G. and A. N.; Investigation, I. L.; Data curation, A. N.; Validation, I. L.; Writing—creating the initial design, P. R.; Writing—reviewing and editing, P. R., S. G., A. N., and I. L.; Supervision, S. G.; Project management, S. G. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Data are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest concerning the reported research findings.

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